

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D3.4

Policy Recommendations based on the Socioeconomic Evaluation of the Critical
ChangeLab Model

Info Sheet

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Glossary

Table 1 - Glossary of terms

CCLab	Critical ChangeLab
Critical ChangeLab	Democracy meets Arts: Critical ChangeLabs for Building Democratic Culture Through Creative and Narrative Practices
PAR	Participatory Action Research
SEE	Socioeconomic Evaluation
SSE	Social and Solidarity Economies
T3.1	Task 3.1 Process Evaluation

Executive Summary

The Critical ChangeLab (CCLab) project, a Horizon Europe initiative, seeks to strengthen democratic resilience in Europe by engaging youth in participatory, creative, and context-sensitive educational practices. The overarching aim is to counteract youth disengagement from democratic institutions by embedding democracy as a lived, relational practice within both formal and non-formal educational settings.

The CCLab model is grounded in Participatory Action Research (PAR) principles which prioritise experiential learning, shared decision-making, and creative problem-solving. The socioeconomic evaluation presented in this document examines the enabling and constraining factors for scaling and sustaining the model, emphasizing structural, relational, and affective dimensions alongside economic considerations.

Key findings reveal systemic barriers within formal education, including rigid curricula, bureaucratic constraints, and insufficient institutional recognition of participatory practices. Teachers often face workload overload and emotional strain when adopting innovative methodologies without structural support (time, collaboration, advice, resources, curriculum integration). Conversely, non-formal education environments demonstrate greater flexibility and interdisciplinary capacity but remain vulnerable to short-term funding cycles and project-based implementation, limiting continuity.

The evaluation underscores the critical role of relational infrastructures—trust-based relationships, emotional safety, and pedagogical adaptability—in sustaining participatory initiatives. These invisible forms of labour, alongside visible resources such as time and funding, are essential for institutionalizing democratic education. Furthermore, the analysis highlights the affective costs borne by educators and facilitators, including vulnerability, professional insecurity, and burnout risks, which must be addressed through collective and systemic measures.

Youth engagement indicators, such as retention rates and energy investment levels, reveal that meaningful participation is less dependent on attendance and more closely linked to participatory design, thematic relevance, and creative facilitation. Consultative processes aligned with socially significant topics consistently yield higher engagement, while directive approaches produce variable outcomes influenced by contextual factors.

Policy recommendations emphasize the need for structural integration of democratic education within curricula, sustainable funding models, and institutional incentives for

innovative practices. Continuous professional development for teachers and facilitators emerges as a strategic priority, requiring decentralized training platforms and flexible frameworks to adapt methodologies to diverse contexts. Additionally, fostering community partnerships and embedding outreach as a systemic function within educational institutions are identified as key strategies for bridging the gap between schools and society.

In conclusion, the long-term viability of the CCLab model depends on moving beyond project-based support toward systemic reforms that institutionalize participatory practices, recognize relational and affective labour, and align policy discourses with enabling structural conditions. Democratic education must be reframed as a core institutional responsibility, supported by sustainable resources and collaborative ecosystems that empower both educators and youth as agents of social change.

Key Insights

- **Relational Infrastructures:** Which can be defined as invisible yet essential elements, such as trust, emotional safety, and pedagogical adaptability, all of which sustain the CCLab as a PAR practice.
- **Youth Engagement Indicators:** Metrics such as retention rates and energy investment levels can be used to assess behavioural and affective participation.
- **Structural Integration:** Educational systems are to formally embed democratic education within curricula, institutional policies, and professional development frameworks to ensure its consistent application and long-term sustainability.
- **Emotional Costs:** Educators and facilitators may experience significant emotional and relational demands, which could potentially influence the feasibility and sustainability of innovative pedagogical approaches.
- **Community Outreach:** It is ideal for educational institutions to establish strategic partnerships with external actors to strengthen civic engagement and enhance the real-world relevance of learning experiences.

1. Introduction

Critical ChangeLab project is a Horizon Europe initiative that aims to build a more resilient European democracy through the implementation of a series of experimental laboratories in which young people engage in diverse artistic and creative exercises. The purpose of these labs is to foster critical consciousness and promote a hands-on approach to everyday democracy within participants' immediate contexts.

To this date, the CCLabs have engaged 2057 students and 270 educators across 19 European countries. Moreover, there have been collaborations with 52 formal and 46 non-formal education institutions, as well as 58 external partners, including NGOs and creative and artistic associations.

The Critical ChangeLab methodology engages youth in identifying, analysing, and addressing social tensions that affect democratic life. Through five phases –grounding, co-constructing knowledge, envisioning, putting into practice, and reflecting together—it fosters critical literacies, collective inquiry, and creative action toward equitable and sustainable futures through participatory, context-sensitive, and reflective democratic education practices.

The pertinence of this project is directly linked to the growing detachment and distrust towards democratic institutions on the part of European youth. For more than ten years, the European Union and the Council of Europe through their Youth partnership have called upon studies that seek to understand the evolving relationship between youth and democracy (Council of Europe, 2014). The critical role of the education sector in fortifying intergenerational cohesion, meeting youth's calls for societal integration alongside personal autonomy, and providing a future-oriented framework has been a continuous motivation throughout the CCLab route of action. Consistent evidence of the project's operative proposals can be found at Milanese, et al. (2025).

Throughout its lifespan, the Critical ChangeLab has engaged in a comprehensive research process encompassing multiple implementation cycles. It began by examining the contemporary state of democracy within educational institutions through a self-assessment tool while simultaneously foregrounding young people's perspectives on everyday democratic practice (Jokić et al., 2024b; 2024c). Building upon this diagnostic foundation, the project designed and co-created, in direct partnership with young people and key stakeholders, an adaptable model of democratic pedagogy applicable to both

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formal and non-formal learning environments (Durall et al., 2024 and Durall et al., 2026). This process unfolded across four Participatory Action Research cycles, during which a rigorous evaluation phase was implemented in parallel (T3.1), generating concrete, evidence-based recommendations for educational policies and practices.

At this stage, the model has reached a level of maturity in which the key elements underpinning its successful implementation have been refined. The project is now oriented towards identifying strategies to scale the model and to ensure the long-term sustainability of both the pedagogical framework and its outcomes beyond the project's initial duration. In alignment with the core principles of PAR, the scaling process is best approached through a systematic scanning of the relevant stakeholder ecosystem, enabling a contextualised understanding of how the pedagogical framework can be adapted, negotiated, and sustained within diverse institutional settings and specific socio-educational contexts.

In this sense, a socioeconomic evaluation (SEE) can offer valuable insights into both the costs, understood in a broad sense, as well as the implications associated with implementing and innovating PAR initiatives, such as the Critical ChangeLab. The analytical framework adopted in this document is rooted in the field of the social and solidarity economy (SSE). Consequently, it relies on qualitative methods, prioritizing the assessment of participation and levels of commitment to the process over the financial costs of technological or artistic materials. Furthermore, the wide variation in economic conditions across contexts demands more complex adaptive efforts –not only in material provisions but also in relational infrastructures– to sustain such initiatives, an issue this report seeks to shed light on.

The first step in diagnosing the European cultural ecosystem involves revisiting the mapping of democratic practices across formal and non-formal educational programs. Previous policy briefs have highlighted significant differences in the democratic approach across formal and non-formal institutions, reflecting distinct conceptualizations of democratic practice (Baketa et al. 2024). In formal educational institutions, democracy is primarily articulated through a focus on structural equity and access, emphasizing equal opportunities across socio-economic backgrounds and ensuring comparable chances for students to complete their education. Within this framework, democratic practices tend to be framed as systemic and institutional responsibilities, embedded in policies, regulations, and organizational arrangements. By contrast, non-formal educational institutions place greater emphasis on democratic processes and participation within the programme itself, foregrounding the inclusion of diverse viewpoints and the cultivation of constructive conflict resolution. In these settings, democratic practices are more directly integrated into

pedagogical interactions, shaping everyday educational relations and participatory dynamics.

Regarding the relationship between the recognised importance of democratic practices and their actual implementation, a consistent pattern emerges across both formal and non-formal educational settings in relation to community outreach. In both contexts, such practices tend to remain largely confined within the institution, reinforcing a degree of organizational insularity and limiting the development of sustained external connections. This suggests that democratic practices are predominantly understood as internal processes rather than community-oriented engagements. In formal educational settings, the least developed practices involve sharing outcomes and evaluating impact with the wider community, indicating persistent challenges in extending the institution's democratic mission beyond its immediate boundaries. Non-formal educational settings display a similar tendency, as the dissemination and external evaluation of outcomes are likewise accorded low priority; however, these settings more strongly embed access for diverse community groups within institutional policies, reflecting a comparatively closer alignment with community diversity. Overall, across both sectors, the limited emphasis on communicating outcomes and assessing impact beyond the institution underscores a shared orientation of inwards democratic management instead of an outward democratic projection.

It is also pertinent that practices granting learners influence over content and methods are marginalized in both educational settings, though for distinct reasons. In non-formal contexts, they are often dismissed as having low importance. In formal settings, the issue is more complex: while democratic principles are frequently embedded within curricula, their implementation is constrained by standardized systems and the rigid timeframes of the academic cycle. This systemic limitation presents a challenge to a core tenet of the CCLab model: that everyday democracy must be an embodied, lived practice that should engage young people meaningfully beyond the classroom through co-creation of significant knowledge. By experiencing democracy in daily interactions, young people cultivate a politically active disposition rooted in experience rather than abstract knowledge. Such participatory practices simultaneously strengthen interpersonal and community bonds while fostering a durable sense of civic responsibility and accountability. In this sense, co-creation in the CCLab has functioned as an overarching concept expressed through multiple co-design moments in which young participants have collaboratively explored, planned, and learned about a specific social concern (Durall et al., 2024).

Finally, top practices in educational contexts reveal distinct orientations in the outcomes domain across formal and non-formal settings. In formal educational settings, such practices are primarily oriented toward the development of students' competencies for active citizenship, with a future-oriented goal of equipping learners with the knowledge, skills, and dispositions necessary for democratic participation beyond the educational context. In contrast, non-formal educational settings emphasize the systematic use of participants' feedback to refine and improve programmes, reflecting a reflexive and cyclical orientation in which outcomes are directed toward the continuous development of the institution or programme itself rather than exclusively toward individual learner trajectories.

Overall, these findings were progressively internalized by the Critical ChangeLab as both a diagnostic insight and a design imperative. The identification of inward-oriented democratic practices, limited learner influence, and persistent challenges in connecting educational experiences to broader community and civic life informed the development of a pedagogical model deliberately oriented toward lived, participatory democracy. Focusing on experiential and youth-centered methods, the CCLab model responds to existing educational needs while directly fighting youth disengagement. It achieves this by redefining democracy as something concrete, relational, and practiced daily in both formal and non-formal settings.

2. Youth and Democracy Engagement.

Critical Changelab Indicators

Drawing upon the findings of the case studies developed in Deliverable 1.3 “Youth perspectives on everyday democracy”, the key challenges to young people’s democratic participation are multifaceted and deeply entrenched (Jokić et al., 2024b).

A pervasive theme is the experience of being unheard or devalued by adult-led institutions. This widespread sentiment fosters a low sense of democratic efficacy, understood as scepticism that participation will lead to meaningful change. These perceptions are further compounded by structural social inequalities and discrimination, which generate psychological barriers and reinforce the belief that democratic spaces are not intended for them. At the same time, significant mental health pressures, exacerbated by constant engagement with toxic social media environments, erode the emotional capacity required for sustained civic engagement. These challenges are therefore framed within a profound distrust of institutions, including schools, law enforcement, and political systems, which are widely experienced as unresponsive and closed off.

Despite the significant barriers to participation, there are also several enabling factors that are key for young people’s democratic participation. First, dedicated youth programs function as crucial micro-democratic spaces where they feel heard and valued. Second, the presence of positive facilitators, mediators and allies further eases institutional distrust and models democratic interaction. Concurrently, both online and offline peer communities and collective identity groups provide a foundation of belonging that strengthens political voice and facilitates respectful debate. Underpinning these factors is a widespread, often implicit, democratic consciousness: a persistent desire for recognition, fairness, and change that is enacted through individual and collective agency. In this context, agency refers to the ability to step outside an existing frame of action and actively reshape it (Durall et al. 2024). This incipient agency indicates that the seed for democratic relationality often exists even when the official or formal language of democracy is absent.

Ultimately the cross-case analysis of young people’s perspectives demonstrates that everyday democracy is predominantly understood not through formal political institutions, which are often seen as inaccessible, but through relational experiences of voice and fairness in their close contexts. Meaningful participation becomes viable when young people can engage in supportive peer groups that build collective identity, participate in

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safe, relationally-based programs designed as micro-democratic spaces, and encounter committed adult allies who listen and act as intermediaries with formal institutions. Furthermore, engagement is sustained when young people can see tangible outcomes from existing community activism, as this reinforces a sense of efficacy. Crucially, engagement is also fostered when young people encounter contexts, whether digital, local, or institutional, in which their lived experiences and critiques are genuinely validated as legitimate forms of democratic knowledge. Young people repeatedly expressed a desire to be heard yet often faced systems and infrastructures unwilling to listen. Strengthening everyday democracy therefore requires accessible participatory spaces, youth-centred institutional practices, and cross-sector efforts that address inequality and mental well-being. As Woodgate et al. (2020) note, the question of youth voice entitlement is not easily resolved. The core issue is the persistent assumption that young people need adults to legitimise their perspectives, rather than institutions redesigning themselves to listen meaningfully and consistently.

In response to these challenges, the Critical ChangeLab oriented its work toward the development of a democratic pedagogical model grounded in creative and narrative practices aimed at fostering young people's active engagement. To support this objective, the project adopted mixed-methods research through which more than 600 pedagogical methods were tested. Furthermore, the methodological plurality created multiple entry points for participation, thereby enhancing youth engagement and supporting the development of critical thinking.

It is of note that the CCLab also demonstrated a multifaceted engagement with democratic education using contemporary digital methods and technologies across both creative and technical domains. Immersive learning was facilitated through Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality (AR/VR), including an augmented-reality game for media literacy. Technical skills were developed via coding and electronics using BBC micro:bit and Arduino for prototyping, while Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning tools (AI/ML) like Teachable Machines and Large Language Models (LLMs) supported ideation and bias exploration. Digital fabrication was central, with participants exploring Fab Lab makerspace tools like laser cutters, 3D printers, and design software to produce speculative artifacts and activist items. Complementary activities included citizen science mapping with OpenStreetMap, environmental water testing, and professional media production using cameras and sound studios for podcast and video creation. Collaborative technologies such as Mentimeter for live polling and dedicated social media youth platforms facilitated co-creation and dissemination, highlighting a comprehensive, hands-on approach to digital innovation. Additionally, a large variety of artistic, embodied and design-based methods such as

Theatre of the Oppressed, role playing, debate facilitations, zine creation and dear data formed an integral component of the pedagogical framework, ensuring the development of both technical proficiency and critical creative thinking.

Since the Critical Changelab aimed at addressing democratic disengagement, engagement is perceived both as a process and an outcome. Therefore, to capture variations and assess youth engagement across labs, this present Socio-Economic Evaluation (SEE) proposes a mixed method assessment that focuses on two key dimensions: retention rate and observed energy levels during the implementation of the labs. The aim of this analysis is to make visible young people’s levels of involvement, agency, and investment over the process, allowing researchers and policymakers to assess whether participatory conditions are being meaningfully enacted and to adjust pedagogical and institutional strategies to local contexts accordingly.

The retention rate is treated as a quantitative indicator of behavioural engagement, reflecting continuity and sustained participation over time. It was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Retention Rate} = \frac{\text{Final Number of Participants}}{\text{Initial Number of Participants}} \times 100$$

This numerical value represents the percentage of participants retained by the end of the PAR cycle, with values above 100 indicating growth in participation and lower than 100 indicating disengagement to the process. These assistance indicators were systematically registered in researcher’s field diaries throughout the implementation of the CCLabs.

On the other hand, the energy investment level is a qualitative indicator that seeks to capture affective and motivational dimensions of engagement. It was operationalised on a three-point ordinal scale: low, medium, high, with the following observation hints:

Table 2. Energy Investment Level and Observation Hints

Energy Investment Level	Key Process Hints
Low	Participants showed minimal personal connection or reflection. No evidence of change, meaning making, or process ownership.
Medium	Participants showed some level of connection and reflection, but it remained descriptive or surface-level, with limited critical depth.

Energy Investment Level	Key Process Hints
High	Participants showed personal investment, critical reflection, and ownership. Experience led to meaningful insight or some level of transformation.

Source: Own elaboration based on Durall (2024)

These indicators were valued from analysis of focus groups performed with youth participants. However, when such reflection couldn't be implemented due to time constraints, researchers and facilitators provided feedback given their personal observations throughout the labs. It is worth noting that the following indicators pertain to the Critical ChangeLab third PAR cycle, during which an equitable proportion of formal and non-formal educational environments were involved, and the pedagogical model had reached a stage of optimal development. The following table provides an overview of this PAR cycle indicators.

Table 3. PAR Cycle 3 Engagement Indicators

Country	Educational Setting	CCLab Topic	Participation Process	Retention Rate	Energy Investment Level
Austria	Formal Education	Conflict management at classroom	Directive and researcher-led	115.8	Medium
	Formal Education	Youth agency and future envisioning	Consultative with shared decision making	81.3	High
	Non-Formal Education Environment	The future of work	Consultative with shared decision making	100	Medium
Italy	Non-Formal Education Environment	Gender Stereotypes	Consultative with shared decision making	100	High
France	Formal Education	AI	Consultative with shared decision making	66.7	High

Country	Educational Setting	CCLab Topic	Participation Process	Retention Rate	Energy Investment Level
	Formal Education	AI	Consultative with shared decision making	77.3	Medium
Croatia	Non-Formal Education Environment	Food waste	Collaborative and democratic	50	High
	Non-Formal Education Environment	Mental health and youth self-perception	Collaborative and democratic	108.3	Medium
	Non-Formal Education Environment	Substance use and addiction	Collaborative and democratic	77.8	High
Slovenia	Non-Formal Education Environment	Democracy and technology with a maker approach	Directive and researcher-led	36.1	Medium
Greece	Formal Education	Justice and Inclusion	Consultative with shared decision making	100	High
Ireland	Formal Education	Social injustice and the future of the community	Consultative with shared decision making	95.7	High
	Non-Formal Education Environment	Technology, sustainability and the local city	Consultative with shared decision making	78.9	Medium
	Non-Formal Education Environment	Technology, sustainability and community	Consultative with shared decision making	81.3	Medium
Spain	Formal Education	Digital technology and democracy	Directive and researcher-led	93.8	Medium

Country	Educational Setting	CCLab Topic	Participation Process	Retention Rate	Energy Investment Level
	Formal Education	Injustices within classroom settings	Consultative with shared decision making	75	High
	Formal Education	Injustices within classroom settings	Consultative with shared decision making	70	Low
Finland	Non-Formal Education Environment	Empowering and inspiring messages for youth	Consultative with shared decision making	100	Medium
	Non-Formal Education Environment	AI and decision making	Directive and researcher-led	100	High
Netherlands	Formal Education	Disinformation and its impact on democracy	Directive and researcher-led	100	Medium
	Formal Education	Disinformation and its impact on democracy	Directive and researcher-led	100	Medium

Source: Own elaboration based on Process Evaluation (T3.1)

The table reveals several salient patterns related to participation processes, educational settings, and levels of engagement. Overall, higher scores are most consistently associated with consultative processes characterized by shared decision-making, particularly when these align with socially relevant topics. This pattern is especially evident in formal educational settings, as illustrated by the cases of Greece and Ireland, and is also observable in selected non-formal education contexts. Notably, however, the CCLabs do not appear to generate a significant increase in attendance rates. Indeed, only two laboratories recorded a marginal rise in participant numbers: one in a non-formal education setting in Croatia and another in a formal education setting in Austria. It is worth noting that increases in attendance do not correspond with high energy levels. These findings suggest context-specific anomalies that warrant further investigation.

As seen in Figure 1, formal education environments tend to exhibit more stable and higher retention rates on average, possibly due to structured attendance expectations. Retention rates in non-formal settings show greater variability likely due to voluntary participation, less rigid schedules, and variable youth motivation. In these contexts, retention appears more sensitive to topic appeal and participatory processes than in formal settings, where attendance is often mandatory.

Meanwhile, twelve labs reported a decline in attendance. This finding suggests that engagement is less dependent on sustained participation throughout the entire process and is more closely shaped by participants' interactions with key pedagogical moments. This pattern is exemplified by the cross-referencing of reduced attendance rates and energy levels. Specifically, among the twelve labs that registered a decrease in attendance, six demonstrated high levels of energy investment, as observed in Austria, Croatia, France, Ireland, and Spain. This may indicate that reduced attendance does not necessarily diminish energy levels or hinder the achievement of meaningful engagement across the process. Finally, it can be stated that medium energy investment can still yield high retention if other conditions, such as consultative processes and relevant topics are favourable.

Figure 1. PAR Cycle 3 Engagement Trends

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Regarding directive and researcher-led approaches, this type of facilitation produces more variable outcomes. On the one hand, a positive engagement example is observed in Finland in the “AI and Decision Making” lab, a case that also included participant stipends, which may have influenced both attendance and energy investment throughout the process. On the other hand, the lowest engagement tiers are recorded in Slovenia and Spain, suggesting the influence of context-specific factors. In the Slovenia lab, the programme’s strong reliance on advanced digital tools may have posed a barrier to sustained participation. Nevertheless, participants who remained in the programme demonstrated adequate commitment and intrinsic motivation toward both the topic and the methodologies. In the case of the Spanish lab, the low engagement values appear to be linked to intrapersonal affective challenges among participants, which led to activities being approached with a degree of apathy and limited reflective depth. This, in turn, underscores the importance of emotional involvement in fostering youth engagement in PAR.

In the case of fully collaborative and democratic processes, these yield relatively consistent but moderate engagement levels, as evidenced in the Croatian labs. It is notable that, although these cases were conducted in non-formal educational settings, they were nonetheless constrained by educational cycle structures, which appear to have affected attendance rates. Overall, the data suggests that attendance alone does not guarantee high engagement; rather, high engagement appears to emerge from the interaction between participatory process design, participants’ energy investment, intersected with shared decision-making process and a creative facilitation style.

At this point attention should be drawn to two of the main concepts that drove the prototype of the CCLab model: agency and co-creation. As mentioned previously agency refers to participants’ ability to transcend established action frameworks and actively reimagine them, while co-creation is the collaborative process of developing shared meanings, strategies, and collective responses. In this sense while co-creation provides the relational and procedural conditions for participation, agency requires sufficient time, openness, and reflexive space for participants to influence not only outcomes but also the direction and methods of inquiry.

Thus, the CCLab reveals a productive tension between these two dimensions. On the one hand, the process enabled multiple co-design moments in which young people and other adult participants collaboratively explored, planned, and learned around a shared issue. On the other hand, the prioritization of producing a concrete outcome – the pedagogical model – within limited timeframes constrained opportunities for participants to exercise agency more fully, particularly in shaping research pathways, redefining problems, or

engaging in deeper thematic exploration. Rather than indicating a contradiction, this tension highlights a central need in participatory educational innovation: balancing outcome-oriented collaboration with process-oriented agency. While co-creation sets the basic structures for participation, agency deepens it. When time, institutional constraints, or project deliverables dominate, co-creation risks becoming primarily consultative rather than transformative.

In this regard, future implementations of the model could strengthen their impact by intentionally designing moments that lower the pace of the decision-making process to expand reflexive dialogue and enable participants to influence not only pedagogical outputs but also the trajectory of inquiry itself. Balancing key pedagogical milestones with context-specific conditions and participatory pacing emerges as a central consideration for sustaining both co-creative collaboration and agential engagement – a core insight of this analysis.

3. Analysis Sample and Method

This section examines the relevant factors that may enable or constrain the development of lifelong and life-wide learning skills within educational initiatives informed by the Critical ChangeLab pedagogical approach. The previous process evaluation (T3.1) identified the main issues as structural and economic constraints embedded within learning environments, professional development needs, outreach limitations, and competence evaluation challenges.

Through the present analysis two other elements emerged as key issues: the hidden relational infrastructures, and the emotional labour required to sustain participatory research processes across learning environments. The central research question that guided the analysis was the following: *What are the social and economic aspects that can spur or inhibit lifelong and life-wide learning skills related to the pedagogical approach underlying the Critical ChangeLab philosophies?*

The analysis adopts a qualitative research design, informed by Flick's principles of systematic qualitative inquiry (2015). Emphasis is placed on methodological rigor through triangulation, iterative design, and researcher reflexivity. The approach is intentionally adaptive, allowing for context-sensitive data collection and interpretation, with the aim of producing grounded insights into the socio-educational phenomena under study.

In this sense, primary data was gathered through 16 semi-structured interviews with educational stakeholders associated with the CCLab Consortium Partners. Interviews were conducted in two distinct tiers to capture multi-level perspectives on the socio-economic dimensions of implementing and scaling CCLabs:

- 1. Micro-Level Interviews (n=8):** Conducted with immediate collaborators (educators, teachers, facilitators) who were directly involved in the PAR cycles of the Critical ChangeLabs. These interviews focused on the on-the-ground socio-economic resource requirements of implementing CCLab pedagogies at the classroom or workshop level.
- 2. Meso- and Macro-Level Interviews (n=8):** Conducted with medium- to high-ranking education officers, some of whom were not directly engaged in CCLAB implementation. These interviews sought to identify structural, institutional, and systemic factors affecting the scalability and sustainability of CCLab approaches, again framed in terms of broad socio-economic costs and enablers.

An interview script was developed based on key thematic issues identified during the evaluation of the iterative PAR cycles. The script guided discussion with stakeholders around the following predefined themes (view Annex):

- Economic and structural constraints within standardized education systems.
- Needs for continuous teacher/facilitator training in art-based methods, participatory research, democratic awareness, and active citizenship.
- Connections between educational settings and external communities or stakeholders.
- Evaluation of critical competences developed through CCLab activities.

A common grid was then developed to identify emerging issues and common patterns across different contexts.

Figure 2. Participatory Research Analysis Framework

Source: Own elaboration based on Palka (2024)

Additionally, to guide the socioeconomic analysis of the CCLab, this study adopts Palka’s (2024) two-dimensional participatory research analysis framework, which positions participatory research projects along a spectrum of goals, which can range from pure scientific knowledge to radical change, and decision-making structures ranging from centralised to decentralised.

This approach enables classification into four broad types of participatory research: instrumental, co-creative, agency-based and sociotechnical. This framework also facilitates a nuanced evaluation of participation quality, power dynamics, and alignment with transformative objectives.

The following table provides an overview of the stakeholders interviewed in this study, disaggregated by role level, sector, and country. To preserve anonymity during analysis, each participant was given a randomly assigned letter and number code. Stakeholders that were involved in the implementation of a CCLab in any of the PAR cycles are marked with the suffix .1, whereas non-CCLab collaborators are marked with .2.

Table 4. Overview of Stakeholders representation in SEE analysis

Stakeholder ID	Role Level	Sector	Country
C1.1	Pedagogue	Non-Formal Education	Croatia
C1.2	City Council Representative	Government	Croatia
D2.1	Educational Manager	Non-Formal Education	Ireland
D2.2	Department of Youth Officer	Government	Ireland
K3.1	Freelance Educator	Non-Formal Education	Slovenia
K3.2	Pedagogue	Non-Formal Education	Slovenia
L4.1	Elementary School Teacher	Formal Education	Greece
L4.2	Regional Educational Officer	Formal Education-Government	Greece
O5.1	Youth Services Coordinator	Non-Formal Education, Government	Finland
O5.2	High School Teacher	Formal Education	Finland

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Stakeholder ID	Role Level	Sector	Country
T6.1	Researcher and Project Manager	Formal Education	Italy
T6.2	Public Library Director	Non-Formal Education	Denmark
U7.1	High School Teacher	Formal Education	Spain
U7.2	Research Centre Director	Formal Education-Government	Spain
W8.1	High School Teacher	Formal Education	The Netherlands
W8.2	Curriculum developer and Program Lead	Non-Formal Education NGO	The Netherlands

Source: Own elaboration based on Stakeholders' interviews

3.1. Diagnosis of Similar Initiatives in Local Contexts

The first step toward exploring the scalability of the Critical ChangeLab model begins with a systematic diagnosis of stakeholders' local contextual needs, focusing on how participatory logics are enabled, constrained, or transformed across formal and non-formal educational settings in Europe. The analysis draws on Palka's core participatory dimensions: epistemic positioning, degree of agency, institutional embeddedness and power redistribution to map out significant tensions and patterns for understanding the alignment between the interventions and the potential adoption environments.

Based on the evidence across diverse contexts, the epistemic positioning of youth, that is, their role in producing knowledge and meaning, varies substantially and appears strongly aligned with participatory tenets in initiatives that treat young people as authors of knowledge, rather than as mere informants or consultees. In settings such as the NGO-led initiatives in Greece, youth generate transdisciplinary narratives through film, photography, and testimony, articulating lived experiences and challenging prevailing power dynamics. Similarly, Denmark's library-based media labs position young people as critical analysts and producers of media, enabling them to develop their own interpretive frameworks rather than receive predetermined civic content. In the Netherlands, certain youth centres frame participation as recognition, where young people experience epistemic legitimacy through the tangible realization that their voice can lead to action. In contrast, formal school

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contexts often frame participation within simulated democratic activities, such as debates, student parliaments, or institutional visits. According to Palka these environments tend to promote a pre-structured and hierarchical knowledge production and therefore youth engagement may manifest itself as procedural rather than generative. The evidence suggests high alignment with participatory principles occurs when youth knowledge is treated as situated, experiential, and generative, and low alignment where participation is confined to representational or procedural formats.

Regarding the degree of youth agency which can range from consultation to substantive decision-making, the contexts vary sharply according to institutional setting. Non-formal environments, such as libraries, NGOs, youth councils, and community maker labs, consistently foster high levels of agency, enabling young people to influence topic selection, choose methods that can range from the artistic, digital or transdisciplinary, and shape visible outcomes aligned with their own priorities. Exceptions within formal education also exist, such as Institutional Maker Lab projects in Spain and Croatia's school and community engagement programme, both of which have successfully embedded student-led inquiry within the curriculum. In contrast, agency is often constrained within traditional school systems: in Greece, for instance, structural barriers prevent schools from proactively selecting external partners, requiring that collaborations be externally initiated and bureaucratically approved, which limits both the frequency and sustainability of outreach. Similarly, in Finland, even where youth express support for participatory initiatives, temporal constraints limit their actual participation. Overall, alignment with participatory research principles is strongest where youth agency is not treated as an educational extra burden but is structurally legitimized through dedicated curriculum time, elective subjects, or institutional mandates that formally recognize youth voice in decision-making processes.

A central insight drawn from the stakeholder's interviews is that the quality and sustainability of participatory youth initiatives are strongly correlated with their degree of institutional embeddedness and legitimacy. A comparative analysis reveals significant differences. On one hand, in contexts where initiatives lack formal integration within school structures, NGO-led projects remain peripheral and short-term. On the other hand, where participation is institutionally recognised through elective subjects, dedicated curricular programmes, or explicit policy mandates, it shifts from symbolic inclusion towards a structurally integrated practice. This is specially the case for the Maker-lab secondary education projects in Spain. In the non-formal education environment, cultural facilities like libraries can provide stable non-school infrastructure that enables youth-led activities. This is the case with Maker labs integrated within Denmark's library system. Finally, it is evident that sustainable, high-quality youth participation programmes require institutional

recognition, formal integration and long-term funding, for them to achieve meaningful and sustained youth engagement.

A critical dimension for evaluating participatory models concerns their capacity to redistribute power and foster institutional reflexivity. Palka’s framework distinguishes between participation that operates within existing structures and that which actively transforms power relations. The present analysis reveals transformative signals arising under two conditions. The first is when young people experience genuine agency within a pedagogical initiative, as exemplified by stakeholder T6.2 who stated that Dutch youth are “allowed to have a say” in the creative process they engage with. The second is when institutions show the reflexivity to expand civic projects, as demonstrated by the School and Community engagement programme in Croatia, as referred to by stakeholder C1.2.

Furthermore, spaces like libraries and NGOs are reframing democracy around voice, confidence, and epistemic recognition rather than the mere transmission of institutional knowledge. Persistent challenges remain in contexts where national curricula restrict school autonomy, where teachers are subject to workload and accountability pressures, and where participation is systematically framed as complementary rather than constitutive of the core educational mission. These tensions highlight that sustainable power redistribution requires not only pedagogical intent but also structural reforms that reconfigure decision-making authority and institutional priorities.

In this sense, the participatory research practices informed by the interviewed stakeholders can be clustered into three types, as shown:

Table 5. Types of Participatory Research Practices

Type of Practice	Key Features	Implications
Peripheral participation	Externally motivated, short-term, project-based initiatives. Presence of youth voice but low integration and institutional sustainability.	Initiatives often depend on external funding, motivated individuals and have a risk of discontinuity.
Embedded but constrained participation	School-based with formal recognition but limited agency due to curricular constraints	Youth involvement is structured but may often become procedural rather than transformative.

Type of Practice	Key Features	Implications
Committed Participatory Ecosystems	Local or regional systems that are able to embed student-led research and decision-making into formal education structures and policies.	Sustainable, legitimized participation aligned with institutional missions that requires long-term funding

Source: Own elaboration based on Stakeholder's Interviews

In summary, the successful integration of pedagogical initiatives such as the CCLab depends fundamentally on structural accommodation through dedicated timetable slots and curriculum alignment, institutional ownership expressed through municipal or departmental support, and practical feasibility ensured by adequate teacher capacity and student availability. Without these enabling conditions, even conceptually well-aligned initiatives remain marginal and temporary. The principal barrier to meaningful participatory research in education is therefore not a deficit in pedagogical capacity, but rather a matter of institutional design. Participatory frameworks flourish where governance structures enable youth to define problems, co-create methodologies, and witness their knowledge being recognized and legitimized. Conversely, when participation remains conditional, time-bound, or externally initiated without systemic integration, it risks being reduced to a symbolic exercise rather than achieving the transformative impact intended.

3.1.1 Stakeholder's Quotes

Curriculum Developer and Program Lead (the Netherlands): Why are young people in some places really heard and seen and therefore participate, and in other places they're not? Why is it that some young people can make their voices heard and others can't?

Education Officer (Ireland): Youth voice is embedded in departmental processes. Young people or their representative bodies participate in working groups, and consultation is seen as a core policy principle based on the right to the voice of the child. It's a standard practice.

Research and Project Manager (Italy): We don't often encounter a project that integrates an arts-based, technology and participatory action-research perspective, especially in terms of methodology and an art-based approach. And students responded positively to our questions regarding their views on democracy, democratic participation, and the role of social media.

4. Critical Changelab Model Feasibility

The following section aims to expand the specific factors that were identified as crucial for the sustainability and scalability of the model. As mentioned earlier, the key issues that guided our analysis included recognizing the economic and structural constraints within each learning environment, the need for ongoing teacher and facilitator training, the capacity for outreach between educational settings and external communities, and the assessment of critical competencies. In addition to these factors, stakeholders identified two emerging issues that provide significant insight into the conditions affecting the model's scalability: the largely invisible organisational and relational structures that support participatory research implementation, and the emotional and affective labour associated with sustaining such processes.

4.1 Economic and Structural Limits

Overall, all interviewees highlight the benefits of the Critical ChangeLab on at least three levels. First, they underline its impact on young people, for whom this type of programme contributes significantly to the development of key competences, such as a critical understanding of how the world works, the ability to work collectively, critical thinking, empathy, the capacity to imagine alternatives, and the strengthening of their own voice and ability to act in society.

Second, broader pedagogical benefits are identified. Among these, interviewees particularly emphasise the creation of safe and trusting spaces with young people, which enable a deeper understanding of their needs and perspectives, as well as the generation of significant changes in relationships between adults and young people, as stated by stakeholder C1.1. Third, from an educational policy perspective, this type of programme is also seen as contributing to the strengthening of links between the education system and society, generating broader opportunities for social participation and community engagement. This insight was shared by stakeholders L4.1, L4.2, U7.1, U7.2, C1.1 and C1.2 from the Greek, Spanish and Croatian contexts. In this sense, long-term benefits for society, including youth empowerment, were pointed to the development of an active, engaged and empathetic citizenship, and the strengthening of a sense of social responsibility (O5.1 and C1.2).

While all participants agree on the multiplicity of benefits that this approach can bring in both formal and non-formal education contexts, reflections on its economic and structural

feasibility are more varied. In this regard, significant differences emerge between the factors that enable or hinder the implementation of such programmes, depending on the context.

4.1.1 Opportunities and Barriers in Formal Education Contexts

Within formal education, as L4.1 notes, “we have to take into account the difference between willingness and feasibility”. In several cases, it is highlighted that although there is a clear willingness among teachers to implement programmes such as the CCLab, the pre-existing structures of the education system do not always make this possible or viable.

Within this framework, one of the main factors determining the feasibility of implementing a project such as the CCLab in school settings is its alignment with institutional aims and emerging educational policies (W8.1, W8.2, U7.1, U7.2 and O5.2). In this sense, coherence with the school’s democratic ethos, and connections to existing national programmes or the school’s own values are key. Clear examples of this alignment can be found in the school interviewed in the Netherlands, where teachers point out that the CCLab’s approach to civic and democratic education, being aligned with the challenges and priorities defined by national education policies, creates a fertile context for its implementation. A similar reflection is shared in Spain, where both staff linked to educational institutions and schoolteachers confirm the alignment of the CCLab’s key objectives with existing programmes. This alignment facilitates implementation and positions the CCLab as an additional resource to expand teacher training and the possibilities for addressing these topics within the educational space. The importance of alignment is also emphasised by C1.2, where attention is drawn to efforts within the national curriculum to foster a stronger connection between society and the education system, as well as to build more consistent bridges between what happens in school and what happens in the world. In this context, the CCLab is once again perceived as a relevant contribution to work that is already underway.

Another key factor for the feasibility of the CCLab is teacher motivation and their willingness to assume, in many cases, an additional workload in terms of both teaching and training. This aspect directly intersects with the main obstacles identified for an effective implementation of the model. Recurrently, stakeholder who are in a teaching role point to curricular saturation and workload overload as significant barriers, stemming both from the volume of assessable content that must be covered throughout the school year and from the structural pressure on teachers’ time.

Within this framework, teacher training emerges as an ambivalent element. On the one hand, it is recognised as a necessary condition for implementing the CCLab in a rigorous, critical and coherent way. The interdisciplinary focus of the approach, and its commitment

to participatory, democratic and transformative pedagogies, requires dedicated training spaces to allow teachers to appropriate the model, adapt it to their context, and develop the necessary competences for its application.

On the other hand, this same training often operates as a double-edged sword. In many cases, training activities for teachers take place outside working hours, during lunch breaks or at weekends, increasing the amount of unrecognised labour and adding to an already existing workload. As a result, a condition conceived as facilitating the implementation of the project may paradoxically become a factor that limits its feasibility and medium- to long-term sustainability, particularly in educational contexts characterised by strong temporal and organisational pressures.

In this context, the risk emerges that the CCLab may ultimately be perceived as an additional element added to the curriculum due to a systemic lack of time. As D2.2 states: “A programme like CCLab risks being seen as another thing being added on to the curriculum, where teachers believe there is no space for this.” When the project fails to be structurally integrated into curricular planning and school organisation, it risks being relegated to the margins, relying excessively on individual motivation and the personal commitment of particularly engaged teachers.

This situation is further aggravated in educational environments with limited organisational flexibility and rigid bureaucratic systems, where teacher workload increases through administrative tasks perceived as having little educational value, and, therefore, motivation to engage in new projects is reduced. In such cases, participation in initiatives like the CCLab can become a form of invisible and poorly recognised work, sustained more by professional ethics and personal commitment than by effective institutional support. This tension highlights a deeper contradiction: that of promoting transformative agency within education systems that, in practice, limit or obstruct change, pedagogical experimentation, and teachers’ initiative. In this sense, excessive bureaucratisation of the school system emerges as one of the main obstacles to the implementation of projects aimed at fostering meaningful connections with society, as well as spaces for critical thinking and transformative agency.

From an educational policy perspective, these findings point to the need to shift the focus away from individual teacher motivation towards the structural conditions that make the implementation and sustainability of approaches such as the CCLab possible. Such programmes must be explicitly recognised and integrated into curricular frameworks, school-level planning, and teacher professional development policies, so that they do not rely exclusively on teachers’ voluntary commitment. Likewise, reducing bureaucratic

burden, increasing organisational flexibility, and formally recognising innovative pedagogical work emerge as necessary conditions for fostering genuine transformative agency within the education system. Without these structural changes, initiatives aimed at strengthening democracy, critical thinking and connections between school and society risk remaining isolated experiences, difficult to scale and sustained at the cost of teacher burnout.

4.1.2 Opportunities and Barriers in Non-Formal Education Contexts

Institutions linked to non-formal education describe a different landscape in relation to the opportunities and difficulties involved in implementing the CCLab model. Among the main advantages identified is the greater organisational flexibility of these institutions, which allows them to design and adapt programmes and initiatives more agilely, in contrast to the rigidity that often characterises formal education. This flexibility facilitates methodological experimentation, adaptation to changing contexts, and the incorporation of participatory and creative approaches. In addition, the interdisciplinary nature of staff working in the non-formal sector is highlighted as a relevant opportunity for developing projects such as the CCLab, which require the combination of educational, artistic, social and community-based competences.

However, alongside these opportunities, non-formal education institutions identify significant structural challenges. One of the main challenges relates to funding, and to its sustainability over time. In many cases, these institutions depend on competitive calls, project-based funding or short-term financing, which makes it difficult to ensure the continuity of initiatives such as the CCLab beyond the formal duration of the European project. This project-based funding logic limits the ability to consolidate teams, develop long-term processes with young people and communities, and sustain the educational and social impacts promoted by the model itself.

In parallel, another challenge identified in relation to the implementation of the CCLab in non-formal contexts concerns the difficulty of attracting young people to programmes explicitly focused on democracy. As noted by K3.1, a freelance educator, “democracy is a less appealing topic for youth, and other non-democracy related programs are more compelling for youth”. Paradoxically, participating institutions also point out that once young people enter the CCLab and become actively involved in the process, the project develops an autonomous and highly motivating dynamic, without requiring significant additional efforts to sustain participation. This apparent contradiction highlights that the issue does not lie in a lack of interest in democracy per se, but rather in how democracy is articulated as an educational

proposal and lived experience. In this sense, the CCLab appears to function as an experience capable of reconfiguring young people’s relationship with democracy, shifting it from an abstract object of learning towards a situated, relational practice linked to collective action, creativity and social transformation. From an educational and youth policy perspective, these findings point to the need to rethink both funding frameworks and pedagogical approaches to democratic education in non-formal contexts.

Table 6. Economic and Structural Limits and Constraints

Context	Main Identified Issues	Educational Policy Implications
Formal Education Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participatory research is seen as an extra workload, not structurally integrated. Implementation may rely on unpaid teacher overtime, causing burnout and long-term unsustainability. Administrative overload and inflexibility undermine time and motivation for pedagogical innovation. Institutional alignment exists, but structural support for long-term success is lacking. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participatory research initiatives should be embedded into core curricula and funded time for teachers should be provided. Reduced administrative burdens and long-term structural support may ensure sustainability and innovation. Equitable workload distribution should be encouraged across educational institutions systems.
Non-Formal Education Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short-term project funding undermines long-term planning, stability, and program sustainability. Framing initiatives around democracy hinders youth recruitment, as it is perceived as less appealing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educational Policy Innovation programs should shift from single project calls to multi-year funding. Consider reframing democratic initiatives alongside artistic and/or technological methodologies to boost youth appeal.

Source: Own elaboration based on Stakeholder's Interviews.

4.1.3 Stakeholder's Quotes

Freelance educator (Slovenia): The barriers for this kind of programs are mostly

expectations and interests of parents and youth who apply. Our program has a reputation for a more science and art-based approach that makes democracy a less appealing topic. There are other non-democracy related programs that are more compelling for both youth and parents which compete with the labs.

Pedagogue (Croatia): Through the CCLab what was most interesting was learning how to create an additional safe and trusting environment for these students –an environment in which they would open up more. We gained a better understanding of their needs and perspectives, and with that deeper understanding we ourselves gained personal and professional confidence, because we’re working with them and discussing topics that aren’t traditional.

4.2 Continuous Teacher and Facilitator Training

Continuous professional development for teachers and facilitators emerges as a critical priority in fostering democratic awareness, active citizenship, and creative pedagogical practices within both formal and non-formal education systems, as noted by interviewed stakeholders. The following section will address the perceived priority of these initiatives, the barriers and the organizational policies that are already being implemented to provide facilitator and teacher training that advances towards more democratic learning environments and prepare learners for meaningful participation in contemporary social life.

4.2.1 Formal and Non-Formal Education Priorities

In the field of formal education, interviewees highlight the need for practical training for teachers in facilitation, classroom management and participatory methodologies as a key priority. Although there is a recognised growing interest in creative and democratic approaches, overcoming the lack of tools and confidence to integrate them effectively into everyday practice is identified as a priority.

Another key priority is to support the change in the role of teachers, which involves a shift from traditional methodologies to creative, artistic, participatory or innovative approaches. This shift is perceived as particularly challenging for those who have built their practice around models focused on the traditional transmission of content. Likewise, there is a recognised need to acknowledge and promote the value of art as a learning process, insofar as it can activate new forms of participation and involvement among students in the classroom.

In non-formal education contexts, interviewees highlight the connection between

participatory processes and artistic practices, emphasising that participatory approaches are what give educational practice its democratic value. In this framework, art is conceived as a means of experiencing participation in an embodied and affective way. At the same time, it is considered a priority to avoid the trivialisation of artistic strategies through prior training and experimentation by teachers. Likewise, the use of participatory approaches is consistently identified as a priority, due to their cross-cutting, relational nature, as well as the possibility of delving deeper into a topic, changing thoughts about it, or generating a sense of agency among participants.

Overall, interviewed stakeholders that represent educational and cultural organizations (C1.2, D2.2, L4.2, O5.1, U7.2 and W8.2) identify teacher training as a strategic priority and a structural tool for strengthening innovation in the education system, especially in contexts characterised by cultural and linguistic diversity or geographical isolation. Added to this is the concern that professionals acquire skills that enable them to respond effectively to the challenges of the new generations, for whom it is essential to acquire cross-cutting skills such as democratic thinking, critical literacy and civic engagement, with objectives such as understanding power structures to participate meaningfully in social life. Flexibility in the design and implementation of this type of intervention is also highlighted as a priority, so that it can be adapted to local realities and the characteristics of students and teachers.

4.2.2 Identified Barriers in Formal Education

In the field of formal education, the difficulty of fitting these types of methodologies into the curriculum and organisational framework within the established timetable and educational framework is repeatedly pointed out. The rigidity of the curriculum and the structure of time appear to be major obstacles. Another central barrier is the emotional and professional cost of sustaining non-traditional approaches or working with methodologies outside the teaching specialty. Implementing the model means giving up, at least partially, the security provided by mastery of one's own discipline, leading to professional insecurity or emotional exhaustion. This methodological shift is exacerbated by constant exposure to criticism, both internal and external, when practices that challenge dominant educational models are adopted. In the same line motivation and involvement of young people may hinder when exposed to unsupported experimental educational methodology. The need to continually justify these pedagogical decisions increases the emotional burden on teachers.

Finally, there is a pragmatic resistance to incorporating new approaches, such as artistic ones, due to the additional training requirements they entail, as noted by U7.1. Although there is a certain openness to these methods, this is usually conditional on them being part of a clearly defined institutional project that guarantees access to adequate resources and training.

4.2.3 Identified Barriers in Non-Formal Education

In the field of non-formal education, one of the main barriers identified is the lack of clearly assigned institutional responsibility for promoting this type of initiative. In many cases, implementation of the model is dependent on the individual will of educators or facilitators, which limits its scope and continuity. In this regard, it is noted that even when there is interest, traditional methodologies are perceived as a safer and less demanding option. Related to this lack of structural responsibility, there is a shortage of support and tools for working on democracy through the facilitation of participatory processes. The question of who should take responsibility for introducing this type of initiative is explicitly raised, emphasising that there is no clear framework to guarantee this.

Another significant barrier is the problem of sustainability, especially when the model is implemented as a one-off experience linked to research projects or isolated initiatives, without institutional recognition that would allow for its continuity. In these cases, the system's ability to embrace the value of the model and build it collectively is called into question. Time also repeatedly appears as a central barrier. Task overload and limited availability make it difficult to participate in training and to prepare for facilitating participatory processes and complex debates. In particular, the additional time required by educators when working on content with which they do not feel fully confident is highlighted. The attitude and preparation of facilitators, as well as their ability to interact with young people in participatory contexts, are also identified as barriers. In this regard, the importance of having suitable mentors to accompany these processes and support educators in implementing the model is emphasised. In this regard, the need for specific support to implement methods such as artistic ones, which are often perceived as particularly demanding in terms of skills, professional confidence and accompaniment, is highlighted, reinforcing the idea that without external support or mentoring, these approaches are difficult to sustain over time.

4.2.4 Feasibility and Costs of Teacher Training in Formal Education

In the field of formal education, the implementation of the model is considered possible but strongly conditioned by organisational and human factors. Material costs are generally considered acceptable, while human resources are seen as the main challenge, especially in terms of time, training, energy and emotional strain on teachers.

It is underlined that the viability of these processes cannot be sustained solely by small teams or isolated initiatives, since, without a specific time frame, collective spaces are absorbed by logistical and organisational tasks. Likewise, the implementation of the model implies a change in the educational paradigm, shifting the focus from performing exercises

to training critical thinking. This shift entails a significant emotional cost, especially when there is no clear institutional support.

In this regard, the difficulty of teaching using non-traditional approaches is recognised. Despite these difficulties, the testimonies indicate that viability increases significantly when there is clear institutional prioritisation, both at the level of policy decisions and time management. Investment in training and support is seen as a matter of priority within the educational centre.

Finally, the need for external funding to enable teachers to access additional training is identified as a structural limitation, given that many schools do not have extra internal budget for this type of initiative. Consequently, the implementation of the model in formal education appears to be closely linked to access to external resources and sustained institutional support.

4.2.5 Feasibility and Costs of Teacher Training in Non-Formal Education

In the field of non-formal education, the implementation of this type of model is viewed particularly positively, as there are practices already in place that have proven to be sustainable over time. Stakeholders C1.1, D2.1, and O5.1 cited examples of centres and projects that have successfully implemented these approaches on an ongoing basis, reinforcing the perception that the model can be integrated without the need to create entirely new structures.

A key opportunity for the implementation of the CCLab model is its integration into existing programmes and dynamics within non-formal contexts. This logic of integration makes it possible to reduce the costs associated with implementing the model by taking advantage of resources, time and structures that are already operational, and favours a progressive adaptation of the approach without generating organisational overload.

Support networks, observation and peer learning are also identified as viable, low-cost strategies. Overall, the viability of the model in non-formal education is based on its adaptability, the possibility of integrating it into existing structures and the use of collective learning dynamics that favour progressive and sustainable implementation without generating a high economic burden.

4.2.6 Organizations Stance regarding Teacher Training

From the perspective of educational organisations, the barriers to implementing the model are described primarily as systemic barriers, closely linked to the centralisation of the

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education system, which limits the flexibility needed to adapt participatory and creative approaches to diverse local contexts. Added to these limitations is the shortage of staff, infrastructure and time, which is particularly acute in geographically isolated areas. The lack of human and material resources, together with the overload of teaching staff, appears to be a significant obstacle to sustaining this type of initiative.

Another key barrier is the difficulty of sustaining implementation in the long term, both in terms of continuity and funding. The absence of stable economic and structural support mechanisms limits the possibility of consolidating the model beyond specific experiences or time-limited projects. Political and ideological resistance related to the definition of the role of the school has also been identified. At this level, there is a persistent perception that such approaches do not fall within the remit of educational institutions. The willingness and availability of teaching staff also emerge as a significant barrier from a systemic perspective. Furthermore, it is difficult to find enough teachers willing to engage in the development of innovative methodologies, especially in a context of training overload and additional unpaid work.

It was also emphasised that training in innovative methods depends largely on the educational context. Although teachers can research and design work proposals, the effective implementation of the model requires specific training and access to materials and methodologies that are not usually present in everyday practice, which constitutes an additional challenge for its implementation. Stakeholders observed that, the viability of implementing this model is seen as dependent on the allocation of public funding from central authorities. It is explicitly stated that educational institutions do not have sufficient budgetary autonomy to undertake this type of large-scale programme or to develop the necessary infrastructure, which places the responsibility for its implementation at the government level.

In this context, the introduction of such models is seen as a structural investment in the education system, linked to processes of innovation and long-term sustainability, rather than as a one-off expense. However, it is recognised that the main short-term cost is not financial, but rather temporal: the time needed to properly implement these approaches, design consistent programmes and support the processes of pedagogical change. In the long term, economic costs are also identified, as well as levels of uncertainty related to the fit of these initiatives within existing educational frameworks.

In response to these limitations, the development of programmes, platforms or knowledge transfer centres aimed at the professional development of teachers is proposed as a strategic opportunity. These structures would make it possible to concentrate training efforts, ensure continuity and facilitate training processes adapted to different educational

contexts. The objective of these initiatives is not limited to the acquisition of new tools but also aims to strengthen teachers both professionally and personally, promoting a greater willingness to take pedagogical risks when transferring knowledge to new generations. Overall, the viability of these proposals from a policy perspective is linked to the ability to articulate public funding, long-term vision and stable professional development structures that enable educational innovation to be sustained in a coherent and equitable manner.

Table 7. Teacher and Facilitator Training Constraints

Context	Main Identified Issues	Educational Policy Implications
Formal Education Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unyielding curriculums and timetables constraints, alongside the emotional-professional burden on teachers, present challenges for integration of art-based and participatory methodologies. Training in facilitation, artistic and participatory methods is a strategic priority yet resistance to new artistic methods persists due to extra training demands. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National curricular frameworks are in urgent need of revision to include dedicated, flexible time for arts-based and participatory learning, supported by teacher workload adjustments. Accredited training in facilitation and participatory arts could be integrated into in-service professional development, with allocated time, financial incentives and recognition.
Non-Formal Education Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PAR initiatives, such as CCLab can leverage operational resources, time and structures already present in the non-formal ecosystem. Adaptability, peer support and integration into existing structures could enable low-cost, sustainable implementation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funded partnerships between schools and established non-formal youth organizations to co-host and resource PAR cycles should be encouraged. Open-source, adaptable PAR toolkits should be developed, and peer-learning organizational networks should be supported to reduce implementation costs and support scalability.
Organizational Stance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highly centralized education systems lack the flexibility to adapt participatory methods to local needs and diverse contexts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Schools' budgetary and curricular autonomy should be promoted enabling schools to tailor participatory methods to

Context	Main Identified Issues	Educational Policy Implications
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long-term sustainability is obstructed by severe shortages in staff, time, funding, and stable structural support. Successful PAR implementation is framed as a long-term structural investment in innovation, not a one-off expense, requiring public funding and government-level responsibility. 	<p>their local community's specific needs and contexts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To ensure coherent support for systemic innovation, cross-sectoral coordination must align long-term funding, professional development, and educational accountability frameworks.

Source: Own elaboration based on Stakeholder's Interviews.

4.2.7 Stakeholder's Quotes

Curriculum developer and Program Lead (the Netherlands): I always think there's a bit of a risk with art. It seems that anyone can do it and that it then becomes crafting. And when it comes to democracy, teachers may not always feel sufficiently supported or feel that they have the tools to engage in difficult conversations.

Research Center Director (Spain): This approach also involves a significant emotional dimension for teachers, as it takes us out of our comfort zones and requires personal transformation before we can bring it into the classroom. It involves shifting, mobilizing, and unsettling beliefs, values, and ideologies. Teachers often encounter resistance in this daily work.

Educational Officer (Greece): In general, the priority should be flexibility: allowing teachers to adapt art-based and participatory approaches to their local context and student population.

4.3 Community Outreach and Connections with the Outside

Effective community outreach is vital to fostering civic engagement and enriched learning, yet its systematic implementation remains elusive across most educational systems in both formal and non-formal educational environments. This section aims to analyse how this outreach could become feasible, the opportunities it entails, and which are the barriers for its viability.

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According to U7.1, U7.2, a central benefit repeatedly highlighted is the authenticity that community collaborations bring to learning processes. Outreach partnerships enable students to engage with real-world issues alongside identifiable actors within their immediate contexts, thereby allowing learners to apply curricular concepts in concrete settings. Such experiences support the development of first-hand engagement with civic participation, social responsibility, and accountability. Another significant insight shared by U7.1, O5.1, W8.1, C1.1 and D2.1 was that participants were consistently described as more motivated, engaged, and responsive when their work had visible relevance beyond the learning environment. Similarly, stakeholders also mentioned that meaningful experiences of participatory research were characterised by elements of social recognition with peer members of their local community.

Another significant element that expands across contexts and constitutes a major conditioning is financial stability. Stakeholders consistently identify critical expenditures of time for coordination, staff capacity for facilitation, and substantial invisible labour in relationship-building, translation, and mediation; this was particularly shown by the examples shared by W8.2 and U7.1. Where financial resources do exist, they are typically allocated on a short-term project-specific basis, often earmarked through external sources such as citizenship funds, municipal programmes, or innovation grants, and are managed externally rather than embedded within schools' core operational budgets.

It is worth noting that this type of funding pattern facilitates initial experimentation for educational initiatives but fundamentally undermines sustainability and continuity. However, to secure long-term feasibility, a structural shift is required, including the creation of stable budget lines dedicated to partnership coordination and the formal recognition of outreach and partnership management as legitimate, integral components of educational labour within school systems. This is something that is already being foregrounded in isolated cases shared by stakeholders from Ireland, Croatia and Denmark, where a significant effort is being made to integrate collaborations as a systemic element and structural driver of participatory practice.

The enabling and constraining factors for successful outreach community implementation are highly context-dependent, showing notable divergence between settings. This will be further developed according to their formal or non-formal education affiliation.

4.3.1 Feasibility, Opportunities and Barriers in Formal Education Contexts

The implementation of outreach community collaborations in formal education settings is conditionally feasible but structurally fragile. While there is broad consensus on their

educational value and relevance, particularly for civic, democratic, and applied learning, their sustainability is highly dependent on individual initiative, short-term funding, and contextual enablers rather than embedded institutional frameworks. Feasibility increases where external infrastructures, such as municipal programmes, cultural institutions, vocational networks already exist. However there remains limited potential in systems characterised by rigid schedules, high workloads, and weak coordination mechanisms.

Persistent challenges to community outreach in formal education manifest across four interrelated dimensions First, across all national contexts, the absence of dedicated time and excessive workload pressures create the most significant barrier, as regulated timetables and existing institutional demands leave insufficient room for the coordination and relationship-building essential for sustained partnerships. Second, collaboration remains highly dependent on the initiative of individual educators or administrators rather than on institutional frameworks, rendering partnerships fragile and vulnerable to staff turnover or shifting priorities. Third, there is a pronounced lack of structured policy frameworks, formal incentives, and supportive mechanisms to legitimize and sustain partnerships beyond short-term, project-based engagements. Finally, schools generally possess limited administrative and coordination capacity, lacking dedicated roles or resources to manage communication, documentation, and reporting, which severely constrains the continuity and scalability of collaborative efforts.

One enabling condition for a sustainable community outreach in formal education emerges consistently and unambiguously. That is the presence of a dedicated contact person or partnership coordinator which is deemed essential. The absence of this role leads to a series of predictable failures: partnerships collapse during staff transitions, participatory knowledge outcomes are lost rather than transferred, critical relationships are not maintained, and systematic evaluation does not occur. This is something that is already foregrounded in specific cases such as the Netherlands, where the position of Citizenship coordinator in fact exists, and involves extensive relational and coordination work beyond classroom teaching.

Beyond logistical benefits, U7.2, W8.2, C1.1 and C1.2 highlight the significant equity and inclusion potential of school and community partnerships. Such collaborations can create valuable entry points for students from diverse backgrounds, reduce institutional apprehension about engaging with the wider community, and introduce non-school authority figures who positively shift classroom dynamics. This positions community outreach not merely as an enrichment activity, but as a strategic preventive measure against student disengagement and at-risk behaviours. Crucially, these collaborations

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foster democratic and life competencies; students learn to communicate with adults, navigate institutions, and see themselves as active community members, thereby building agency and preparing for active citizenship.

In summary, this reveals a strong consensus on the transformative value of school-community collaboration for creating relevant, democratic education. However, its potential is consistently hampered by systemic constraints of time and under-institutionalization. The path forward requires moving from heroic individualism toward supported systems, combining the passion of engaged teachers with dedicated liaison roles, strategic resources, and programmatic frameworks that institutionalize partnerships while preserving the human connections that make them meaningful.

4.3.2 Feasibility, Opportunities and Barriers in Non-Formal Education Contexts

Non-formal education environments such as youth services, libraries, NGOs, and cultural institutions tend to be comparatively more active in initiating community partnerships. However, such initiatives are often shaped and constrained by short-term funding cycles and project-based implementation frameworks. A key difference between formal and non-formal educational institutions is that the latter are typically mission-driven rather than curriculum-driven and therefore possess greater autonomy in programming and partnership selection.

The collaborative environment described by T6.2 exemplifies an embedded and highly scalable model of institutional-community partnership. This model is characterized by the strategic integration of outreach into the institution's core identity, the distribution of partnership responsibilities across staff roles, and the implementation of formal systems for registering, evaluating, and maintaining external collaborations. Furthermore, it leverages a public space such as a library as a living laboratory for democratic engagement and applied learning. This approach demonstrates that sustained structural investment in dedicated roles, processes, and spaces can transform community outreach from a peripheral, project-based exception into an institutional norm, offering a replicable blueprint for systemic integration in other formal and non-formal educational contexts.

Another critical cross-contextual finding is that motivation plays a substantial role in fostering meaningful youth engagement within non-formal educational settings. As noted by C1.1, participants may not attend activities unless they are actively motivated to do so, which can result in low turnout for initiatives involving external partners and may ultimately undermine collaboration through partner fatigue. Consequently, the success of outreach

efforts depends significantly on the mediation of educators or facilitators who possess the relational and pedagogical capacity to mobilise interest effectively and sustain participant involvement. This underscores that access and invitation alone are insufficient but structured, youth-centred strategies for fostering motivation constitute a prerequisite for successful collaborative programmes. In this regard, a potential strategy could involve combining the role of a liaison coordinator-mediator from the formal education environment (as suggested by L4.1, L4.2 and W8.2) with a more strategic approach to partnership design from the non-formal educational environment (as described by stakeholder T6.2).

The success of non-formal education community outreach initiatives is often predicated on relational dynamics and infrastructures. Effective partnerships emerge when young people establish meaningful connections with specific individuals, such as mentors or external facilitators; when external actors engage in a process of co-creation rather than merely delivering pre-designed content; and when tangible pathways for follow-up—such as internships or public platforms—are made visible to participants. While these conditions align closely with participatory and youth-centred pedagogical principles, their integration into scalable systems presents several key challenges. These include the difficulty of expanding successful pilot projects beyond anecdotal examples, as noted by the Irish stakeholders. In this sense, the main obstacles are not ideological resistance or financial cost, but time, recognition, and continuity. Where organizations invest in dedicated coordination roles, long-term partnerships, and relational infrastructures, outreach collaborations become a powerful mechanism for youth engagement, civic learning, and social inclusion.

Table 8. Community Outreach Constraints

Context	Main Identified Issues	Educational Policy Implications
Formal Education Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> School-community partnerships rely on individual initiative and short-term projects rather than stable, institutional frameworks for support and funding. Financial instability and the unrecognized labor of coordination and relationship-building consistently condition the sustainability of community partnerships. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> District-level educational offices could manage a specific framework budget to ensure school-community partnerships. Permanent community liaison positions within schools should be created to ensure dedicated, compensated labour for coordinating sustainable partnerships.

Context	Main Identified Issues	Educational Policy Implications
Non-Formal Education Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community initiatives in non-formal education are typically constrained by reliance on short-term, project-based funding cycles, limiting their stability and continuity. Successful youth engagement depends heavily on personal motivation and relational dynamics, making it difficult to scale successful pilot projects into systemic, replicable programs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community non-formal education grants should transition from project-based to multi-year operational funding to enhance continuity, stability, and long-term community impact. Successful toolkits, pilots of training, and staffing models should be systematically disseminated district-wide to boost community outreach.

Source: Own elaboration based on Stakeholder's Interviews.

4.3.3 Stakeholder's Quotes

Elementary School Teacher (Greece): A dedicated partnership coordinator or liaison teacher would be essential to sustain communication and ensure continuity. Teachers would need training and time allocation to plan and supervise activities beyond the classroom. These partnerships require institutional time to build relationships and integrate the collaboration into the educational framework in a sustainable way.

Public Library Director (Denmark): Our entire strategy is based on partnerships. It's a deliberate approach built on three levels: strategic partnerships, program-based partnerships, and network-based partnerships. The idea is that responsibility for partnerships and programming should be pushed as far out into the organization as possible, so it doesn't cluster around leaders. Every staff member needs to be able to work with partners and develop programming. That makes reaching outside the organization very easy, because everyone does it.

4.4. Evaluation of the Critical Changelab Competences

This section addresses the relevance, usefulness and costs of evaluating democratic competences essential for developing frameworks for citizenship education programs. The competences defined throughout the iterative process include critical understanding of the world, imagination and creativity, transformative agency, and democratic disposition. In

this context, stakeholders were asked to assess the relevance of evaluating democratic competences and to report on the potential costs that such an undertaking might incur.

It is worth noting that this final block of questions came at the last part of the conducted interviews, and two of the stakeholders did not respond to them, possibly due to fatigue or time constraints (K3.2 and C1.2). Among the remaining 14 testimonies, two distinct approaches emerged. Some offered general reflections on the questions posed, while others framed their responses in relation to their experience participating in a PAR process. The latter group expressed positive evaluations of the experience and emphasized the relevance of the four identified competencies. However, they did not highlight challenges or difficulties, in contrast to those who engaged in broader reflections on the three guiding questions. It is this second group whose contributions appear most pertinent for informing the development of the socio-economic implications of evaluating democratic critical competences.

4.4.1 On the Relevance of Critical Competences

Most stakeholders agree that these competences are essential and should be integrated into young people's education to equip them for navigating the complexities of today's world (C1.1, D2.1, D2.2, L4.1, L4.2, O5.1, O5.2, T6.1, U7.1, U7.2, W8.1, and W8.2). They emphasize the importance of enabling students to make sense of information and critically engage with news in an environment saturated with stimuli. Additionally, stakeholders highlight the need for young people to develop the ability to critically examine and challenge dominant technological and societal narratives.

Interviewees specifically highlight several key points: the value of curiosity about others and the ability to listen; the limited emphasis placed on reflection and creativity within schools; and the importance of collective reflection, sharing experiences, and publicly demonstrating the learning process as a means of fostering conscious and active citizenship. A critical consideration regarding these competencies is the broader understanding of knowledge—not as rote memorization, but as knowledge connected to real-life situations and contexts. Rather than simply agreeing or disagreeing with the competencies promoted by CCLab, stakeholder U7.1 relates them to those prioritized in projects within her institution. This particular stakeholder, who is also an active teacher, explained that the underlying aim is to engage students in imaginative and transformative processes that allow them to explore the world deeply, recognize the possibility of change, and envision future scenarios, ultimately aligning their personal aspirations with a sense of purpose.

There is a recognized need for providing students with foundational knowledge about democracy before initiating projects such as CCLab, as this is essential for understanding how they position themselves within civic contexts. While several stakeholders emphasize the importance of these competencies, some also acknowledge the challenges associated with implementing them in practice. D2.2, L4.2, U7.1 and T6.1 concur that the four competencies are necessary and should be closely aligned with students' needs, while also noting that they generally receive limited attention in schools. Furthermore, they stress that teaching these skills is extremely difficult yet highly important for enabling students to comprehend concepts such as power, change, and resilience. Workshops, including PAR cycles, are viewed as helpful in addressing this gap, given the insufficient time allocated to civic education in school curricula. However, democratic education is understood as a shared responsibility that extends beyond schools to families and society as a whole.

4.4.2 On assessing Competences at Schools

This question is particularly relevant as it underscores the complexities of integrating CCLab-related competencies into education systems. First, it challenges the beliefs of teachers and families who may resist being questioned. Second, it raises the issue of assessment, which is often approached through standardization; if results indicate that certain skills are not being addressed, alternative strategies should be provided, as is common in subjects such as mathematics or language. Third, it reflects a finding already evident during the questionnaire phase: schools do not necessarily operate as democratic institutions, and opportunities to foster participation, critical thinking, creativity, and imagination may be uneven on certain contexts (Jokić et al., 2024b). Furthermore, this question draws attention to the purpose of assessment, which should not be limited to assigning grades but rather focus on delivering meaningful feedback that enables students to recognize their progress and identify areas for continued learning.

Another significant insight highlighted assessment as a practice that can support both individual and collective growth while engaging the socio-emotional dimension of learning—an interrelationship that could be further considered within further implementations of Critical ChangeLabs. While standardized assessment can generate data to serve as indicators, knowledge linked to democratic competencies is inherently difficult to standardize. The assessment approach is also closely connected to teacher training, enabling educators to focus on conceptual understanding, overarching ideas, and specific competencies. In addition, it should incorporate qualitative elements such as reflections, testimonies, and narratives that capture personal and community development. Another collaborator emphasizes the need for schools to move beyond content delivery and

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help students understand the world and their role within it. For this reason, these competencies can only be effectively implemented and assessed when embedded in concrete projects that provide meaningful contexts for learning.

Regarding the difficulties associated with assessing democratic competences, the evidence indicates that such assessment is necessary yet highly challenging. It intersects with power dynamics between teachers and students, ultimately becoming a matter of relational complexity. All collaborators acknowledge the need to evaluate these competencies while also highlighting several obstacles. These include cultural prejudices; the challenge of monitoring progress over time, not just at as a summative final evaluation; and the risk that compulsory assessment could hinder youth engagement. Further obstacles are the extensive existing curricular content, the implicit nature of these competencies (which must first be made explicit), and the need for teachers to both recognize their importance and ensure compatibility with current curricular frameworks. Additionally, assessment should connect to experiences beyond the school environment and align with research on democratic self-confidence and democratic resilience. Finally, the unique realities of each school context must also be considered.

4.4.3 Costs of Qualitative and Continuous Evaluation of Competences

This issue is critical for a SEE, as it highlights key considerations for implementing democratic education that incorporates the contributions of the CCLab model. Such an evaluation should focus on structural aspects, addressing not only the extent to which education systems engage with democratic and citizenship education, but also how teachers integrate these principles into classroom practice. If the structural framework is not addressed, meaningful change will be difficult to achieve. As U7.1 noted regarding education systems that prioritize academic content, “neither families nor teachers would accept it.” Therefore, as previously mentioned, it is essential to prioritize what must be brought into schools during times of rising authoritarianism in order to safeguard democratic values.

It is considered necessary to quantify the cost of implementing a Critical Changelab; however, establishing indicators for the entire educational process is highly complex. Despite these challenges, the interviews reveal several indicators that could inform political decision-making aimed at promoting democratic education:

- Clearly define the goals of democratic projects.
- Allocate time for prior alignment with teachers, particularly if the objective is to permeate the entire system, classroom practices, and school life.

- Establish clear teaching and assessment criteria.
- Develop a comprehensive teacher development program, as implementing CCLab requires training, resources, and funding—not tied to a single subject, but dedicated to making education democratic.
- Monitor group work more effectively, for example, through student interviews.
- Clarify citizenship education requirements for schools.
- Address resource constraints, especially human resources, and ensure commitment from individual teachers and school leadership to prioritize these initiatives.
- Secure a sustainable budget to meet all these requirements.

The list of situations to which costs are linked is critical for this analysis, as it includes training, time, emotional burden, and budget—all necessary to support the shift implied by competency-based learning. One insight suggests reframing the notion of “costs” as “needs,” emphasizing the time required to design a program that allows these issues to be raised, discussed, and specified with sufficient flexibility. Once the program is implemented, new needs may emerge, potentially generating additional costs. Given that a significant cost lies in the time and involvement required from teachers, it is proposed that administrative burdens be minimized by avoiding excessive paperwork and bureaucratic requirements for schools.

Table 9. Evaluation of Critical Competences

Context	Main Identified Issues	Educational Policy Implications
Formal Education Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Democratic critical competences are vital for youth citizenship education yet remain undervalued and difficult to teach in schools. • Assessing democratic competences requires integrating them into meaningful, applied projects rather than treating them as abstract content. • Qualitative, formative assessment is preferred over standardized testing, yet hindered by curricular constraints, teacher capacity, and cultural biases. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritize funding for structured teacher training to integrate democratic competencies across curricula through project-based citizenship education. • Embed democratic competences in sustained, meaningful learning projects to ensure effective implementation, and learner engagement. • Replace standardized evaluations with portfolio-based

Context	Main Identified Issues	Educational Policy Implications
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Democratic competences' relational, implicit nature complicates evaluation, requiring cultural shifts toward explicit and sustained monitoring. 	<p>assessment systems that document student growth in democratic competencies over time.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish school wide protocols for reflective dialogue and observation to make implicit democratic learning visible and valued within the school culture.

Source: Own elaboration based on Stakeholder's Interviews.

4.4.4 Stakeholder's Quotes

Research Centre Director (Spain): Through this process of imagination and transformation, they learn deeply, discover that change is possible, and envision possible futures, aligning their own lives with that purpose. This is the core objective of everything we do.

Department of Youth and Education Officer (Ireland): Current systems measure literacy and numeracy through standardised outcomes, and these indicators don't necessarily lend themselves well to evaluating democratic or creative capacities. Change is needed, but it will be a journey, particularly because our context performs very well on all the standard outcome indicators, and there may be reluctance to relinquish those as the indicators on which our system is assessed.

Public Library Director (Denmark): Evaluation is important –especially if you want to connect with formal learning institutions. It's a necessity. And that's a crucial point: what kinds of institutions are involved and what's needed to engage them. If you want to reach formal learning institutions, you need to be very curriculum-based, with the risk that young people will see it as schoolwork –something compulsory that they don't relate to.

4.5 Sustaining Relational Infrastructures in PAR

Across formal and non-formal educational contexts, the viability of participatory initiatives pivots on the presence and alignment of both visible and invisible infrastructures. On one

hand regarding the evident infrastructures, it has been shown the foremost requirement is dedicated time and curricular space, yet standardised timetables and short-term project windows often restrict engagement to isolated slots, limiting depth. While basic material resources are generally available, sustainability is undermined by short-term funding cycles tied to individual initiatives and projects rather than embedded structures. Effective implementation also depends on trained human resources, including facilitators and dedicated coordinators, and requires systematic upskilling for teachers. On the same line, institutional consent, formal alignment with curriculum goals and leadership priorities are critical; without this official recognition, even well-resourced projects struggle to scale or endure.

On the other hand, stakeholders consistently identified less tangible infrastructures as decisive for the successful implementation of PAR initiatives, such as the CCLab. The first insight is the substantial relational and affective labour required to motivate voluntary participation, cultivate safe and trusting environments, and navigate the nuanced boundaries between care, authority, and co-creation. One example provided by C1.2 referred to motivation as a relational process that should be actively cultivated and renewed over time. In this sense the creation of safe and trusting environments in which young people feel able to engage plays a key part. Stakeholders previously involved in a Critical Changelab, as C1.1, L4.1 and U7.1 highlighted key moments of transparency which included adults sharing their own vulnerabilities, insecurities, and uncertainties with youth. These practices modelled openness, invited the co-regulation of emotions, and helped normalize difficult or sensitive topics. This co-vulnerability was held within clear boundaries that preserved care, authority, and mutual respect.

Stakeholders like K3.1, T6.2 and D2.2 also highlighted that contemporary youth often favour flexible and spontaneous forms of participation over long, rigid commitments, shifting the affective task toward meeting motivation where it stands and designing processes for variable engagement. Strategies such as modular project cycles, visible milestones, and multiple entry points were identified as effective ways to accommodate fluctuating involvement. Regarding the co-creative process, stakeholders like U7.1 and W8.2 noted that a critical and often unacknowledged form of relational labour involves deep attunement to context and identity, requiring practitioners to adapt participatory methods to students' and teachers' self-perceived limits—such as discomfort with artistic or embodied expression. This affective work entails noticing subtle resistance and designing manageable entry points that safeguard participant dignity and agency. Achieving a sustainable balance between the roles of care, authority, and co-creation involves scaffolding authority, process, and participation.

A second, equally critical insight is the need for a profound pedagogical and cultural shift, which demands that educators transition from content delivery to facilitation, embrace open-ended inquiry over predefined outcomes, and adopt collaborative approaches over isolated practice. This shift often encounters two levels of resistance. On one hand teachers express that this pedagogical proposal requires dedicated time for reflection and collective support. On the other hand, resistance can also be found in the schools' governance system where some stakeholders describe how bureaucratic obstacles often limit their autonomy and possibility of initiative. While such support resources are present in some contexts, they have yet to be structurally embedded in many others, representing a persistent barrier to sustainable implementation.

Another relevant insight regarding hidden infrastructures relates to the often-unacknowledged connective labour, which includes informal coordination, translation between institutional logics, and the contextual adaptation of methodologies. It was often stressed that the long-term sustainability of partnerships is fundamentally dependent on these trust-based relationships, rather than on contractual arrangements alone. A key cross-cutting insight is that visible elements like dedicated time, funding, and training are necessary yet insufficient without the concurrent support of invisible infrastructures, including relational trust, pedagogical adaptability, and emotional safety. Stakeholders like D2.1, D2.2, U7.1, U7.2 and W8.1 consistently observe that when participatory practice becomes "inherent to the institution," embedded within its culture and leadership vision, the necessary time and space can be mobilized for its implementation. Conversely, when support remains project-based or dependent on individual enthusiasm, initiatives remain vulnerable to collapse.

Finally, it is imperative to remember that the implementation of PAR initiatives sit within the scope of politically situated practices, defined by a series of inherent tensions within hierarchical and centralized education systems. A primary tension arises between the democratic, co-creative ethos of PAR and existing governance models, where approval processes and compliance logics frame participation as an authorized activity rather than a shared enterprise. This political struggle is further evident in the curriculum, which becomes a site of contestation where participatory aims must be strategically translated into the language of official learning outcomes to gain legitimacy. Simultaneously, conventional evaluation frameworks, usually focused on quantifiable metrics, marginalize the democratic and affective learning central to PAR, revealing measurement itself as an exercise of power that governs educational priorities. A final, critical tension exists between the policy imperative for scalable, cost-effective models and the participatory need for contextual adaptation and relational integrity, posing a core challenge between bureaucratic efficiency and genuine

youth agency. These tensions highlight that PAR does not operate neutrally but within structures of authority, accountability, and risk-averse culture; its success depends not on avoiding politics, but on navigating these power dynamics to sustain innovation while remaining institutionally viable.

Overall, it can be stated that the long-term viability of PAR initiatives requires institutions to move beyond project-based support and formally recognise the relational, affective, and connective infrastructures that sustain participatory practice. Making this work visible through leadership endorsement, protected time, stable funding mechanisms, and evaluation frameworks that value democratic and relational outcomes is essential for scalability and sustainability. Such recognition is not merely operational but constitutes a deliberate political and pedagogical choice: one that redefines participation as a core institutional responsibility rather than an optional innovation. Without this shift, PAR initiatives remain dependent on one-term commitment and remain structurally vulnerable within hierarchical education systems.

Table 10. Relational Infrastructures

Context	Main Identified Issues	Educational Policy Implications
Formal and Non-Formal Education Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable PAR demands a dual infrastructure of visible resources like time, funding and training, as well as invisible, relational ones like trust, affective labour and cultural adaptation. Relational labour that includes co-vulnerability, attunement, and balancing care with co-creation is essential for safe, trusting environments in PAR. PAR practice implementation is inherently political, as it confronts hierarchical systems, standardized curricula, and demands for quantifiable, scalable models. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognise trust-building and cultural responsiveness as essential, legitimate educational work in all planning and evaluation activities. Promote a protocol or framework that outlines the ethical expectations, concrete relational practices and conflict management procedures for participants in PAR initiatives. Support governance structures that share power with students, families, and communities through co-design and real decision-making authority.

Source: Own elaboration based on Stakeholder's Interviews.

4.5.1 Stakeholder's Quotes

Curriculum Developer and Program lead (the Netherlands): Collaborations require a significant investment of time and energy. Schools must accept this and dedicate someone to manage it—perhaps two days a week to establish the partnership and then maintain it. A great deal of invisible work falls on schools in this process.

Secondary Education Teacher (Spain): A significant barrier in external collaborations is that teachers without personal resources or connections may struggle to establish them. An enthusiastic but inexperienced teacher might not know where to start. While one teacher might be assertive and seek help, another could feel overwhelmed and just aim to complete the project. Even with school support, it is difficult without specific guidance on where to find resources. In this regard, pre-designed programs are very helpful. It is important to give students' work authenticity, allowing them to see that they are responding to real-world situations.

Education Manager (Ireland): Some major constraints we face are short term funding, short term funding cycles and contract cycles. Also, when initiatives are led by specific people, they become vulnerable. There is always that risk that when a programme is led by that specific person that then if they leave, the programme doesn't exist anymore.

4.6 Attending to the Emotional Costs of Participation and Co-Creation

As observed previously, the relational dimension of PAR implementation entails recognising invisible labour and mediating politically situated elements of the research process. However, throughout the stakeholder analysis, affective costs also emerged as a significant factor that operates as a major enabling or constraining condition for the implementation of PAR. These costs were not described as secondary or incidental, but rather as a core, structuring infrastructure that shapes the feasibility, sustainability, and ethical quality of participatory initiatives. Across contexts, stakeholders highlighted the ongoing emotional demands associated with sustaining meaningful youth engagement, particularly in initiatives reliant on voluntary participation. Facilitators noted the need to manage uncertainty related to fluctuating attendance, to continuously support participant motivation alongside competing demands, and to navigate professional challenges when collaborations do not progress as anticipated.

Another emotional cost identified in relation to the relational dynamics of PAR implementation concerns heightened vulnerability and the blurring of boundaries inherent

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in power-sharing practices like co-creation. Facilitators are required to partially relinquish traditional authority roles in order to build trust, while simultaneously managing reduced professional distance, moments of emotional exposure arising from participatory interaction, and the ongoing self-regulation demanded by the facilitation role. These demands are often intensified by institutional pressures, particularly when facilitators must repeatedly justify the legitimacy of participatory research approaches within conventional accountability frameworks. In parallel, educators experience distinct emotional costs linked to pedagogical exposure when working within open-ended and uncertain formats. This includes navigating reduced control over learning processes, responding to critical scrutiny of non-traditional methodologies, and operating under conditions of heightened evaluation. Collectively, these dynamics indicate that sustaining participatory practice requires not only pedagogical competence, but also substantial emotional labour, which remains largely unrecognised and insufficiently supported within prevailing institutional structures.

A consistent finding highlights the significant risk of isolation and burnout, particularly when PAR initiatives are not institutionally embedded. Stakeholders like U7.1 and W8.1 report feeling professionally alone when their pedagogical vision is not shared by leadership or colleagues, and they often become overloaded as informal change agents without structural support. This chronic exposure to resistance creates sustained emotional strain, underscoring that personal conviction is insufficient without collective backing. This identified issue warrants further research into potential correlations with faculty burnout or associated sick leave and any participatory pedagogical innovation practices, given that secondary teachers are particularly vulnerable to elevated stress and burnout syndrome (Montserrat et al., 2025; Lobo-Ortiz et al., 2023; García-Carmona et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the feasibility of PAR is shaped by a broader collective emotional climate. Systemic factors such as general work overload create a fragile baseline for innovation. When initiatives depend primarily on finite personal enthusiasm as an emotional resource, and lack institutional back-up such as recognition or protected time, emotional energy becomes a scarce commodity. Consequently, these emotional costs are not individual pathologies but structural effects of educational systems that externalize the responsibility for care, motivation, and resilience onto individual practitioners. A prior contribution to this line of emotional cost analysis in education innovation can be found in Sancho-Gil and Rivera-Vargas (2016).

In conclusion, the analysis reveals that the affective dimensions of implementing PAR are structural and cumulative, rather than incidental or attributable to individual resilience. The

process demands a significant investment of emotional availability, relational risk, professional vulnerability, and sustained motivational energy from educators. When these costs remain unacknowledged, unsupported, or framed as a personal undertaking, PAR becomes unsustainable. The evidence strongly suggests that emotional sustainability is achievable only when participatory practice is collective, institutionally aligned, and culturally normalized. This shift transforms necessary emotional labour from a private burden into a shared professional condition, thereby converting a critical vulnerability into a foundational element of a supportive educational infrastructure.

Table 11. Emotional Costs

Context	Main Identified Issues	Educational Policy Implications
Formal and Non-Formal Education Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The emotional labour of PAR is not incidental but a core, systemic requirement that dictates its feasibility and ethics. PAR facilitators' professional demand includes managing relational risks such as vulnerability, blurred boundaries, and defending co-creation within conventional frameworks. Without collective support, the emotional labour of participatory practice could lead directly to practitioners' isolation and burnout. The emotional costs are systemic, not individual, stemming from structures that outsource care and resilience onto educators. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide structured professional development in emotional facilitation, including grounding issues, conflict mediation, and boundary setting to equip educators with the necessary skills for an ethical, sustainable PAR practice. Integrate burnout prevention and emotional impact metrics into policy frameworks, mandating workload limits, role rotation, and evaluations of emotional safety and sustainability. Institutionalize team-based facilitation and peer support structures to distribute emotional responsibility, ensuring collective rather than individual burden in participatory practice.

Source: Own elaboration based on Stakeholder's Interviews.

4.6.1 Stakeholder's Quotes

Elementary School Teacher (Greece): The largest cost, however, is human: teachers' time, energy, and emotional investment. Many already manage heavy workloads, so

participating in new training or redesigning lessons demands additional effort

Secondary Education Teacher (Spain): You must constantly defend your methods to those who oppose them, often based on their own limited experiences as students. Since everyone has an opinion on education, this constant criticism is a burden. This emotional strain is a risk for the entire school community, affecting both management and teachers who must defend an unsupported model.

Capital City Council Representative (Croatia): We believe it is important to offer professional development that, on the one hand, strengthens professors emotionally and socially so that they can respond to the challenges of new generations, and, on the other hand, provides them with concrete tools—new knowledge and new skills—that enable them to actively transmit the types of knowledge and activities that we consider important as a local community.

5. Recommendations for Practice

The following sections addresses educational policy recommendations for practice regarding the identified issues throughout the present SEE.

5.1 General economic and structural constraints

Within formal educational settings, participatory and art-based research is often viewed as extra workload, relies on unpaid teacher time, and is hindered by administrative and institutional constraints, with limited long-term support to ensure sustainable, innovative implementation.

Policy measures should prioritise embedding participatory actions in curriculum, reducing administrative burdens and establishing stable, long-term structural support, as well as promoting a more equitable distribution of workloads across educational institutions. This can become operative as follows:

- *Embed participatory research into the core curricula by defining clear learning outcomes, offering ready-to-use teaching materials, and allocating protected hours within teachers' schedules so planning, implementation, and reflection are recognised as a valid part of their work assignments.*
- *Reduce administrative barriers and ensure long-term institutional support through simplified reporting tools, digitalised procedures, and the creation of stable coordinating roles, on school or district-level, to guarantee continuity and foster innovation.*
- *Promote equitable workload distribution by establishing institutional and/or regional guidelines that ensure participatory activities and projects are shared fairly among staff and do not disproportionately burden individual teachers like social study or arts areas.*

Within non formal education settings the main identified issues are short-term funding that undermines stability and planning, and democracy-framed initiatives that fail to engage youth by appearing less appealing to many participants.

In this line, policy measures should consider shifting from single project calls to multi-year funding and reframing democratic initiatives through artistic and technological

methodologies to enhance youth engagement and overall appeal. This can become operative as follows:

- Introduce multi-year funding schemes that allow NGO and other similar organisations to plan, implement, and evaluate participatory initiatives with long-term stability.
- Link this funding to programs that combine democratic themes with artistic or technological activities to increase youth interest and sustained engagement.

5.2 Regarding continuous teacher and facilitator training

Within formal education settings the main identified referred to unyielding curricula, limited time, teacher overload, and insufficient training in artistic and participatory methods, alongside resistance caused by the extra demands such training entails.

Policy measures should address these issues by revising national curricula to include flexible time and adjusted workloads, and integrating accredited, well-resourced training in facilitation and participatory arts into in-service professional development. Operative actions build on previous economic and general constraints policy recommendations and can be enriched as follows:

- National curricular frameworks could be improved for greater flexibility by piloting small-scale flexible-time curriculum models in selected schools and establishing monitoring indicators to ensure robust quality standards.
- Develop accredited in-service facilitation and participatory arts training modules, providing financial incentives for teachers completing certification.

Within non formal educational settings the main findings are that PAR initiatives like CCLab can build on existing resources, time structures and peer-support networks, whose adaptability enables low-cost and sustainable implementation. This already shows a positive disposition towards PAR.

Policy measures should promote funded partnerships between schools and established non-formal youth organisations to co-host and resource PAR cycles, while also developing open-source, adaptable toolkits and supporting peer-learning networks to reduce costs and enable scalable implementation. Operative actions can be materialized as follows:

- *Establish funded partnership agreements between schools and non-formal with joint budgets that cover facilitation, materials, and coordination.*
- *Promote peer-learning networks that connects teachers, youth workers, and facilitators engaged in implementation of PAR and encourage them to review successful experiences that may lead to applicable and adaptable toolkits.*

Additionally, organizational policy measures should promote greater budgetary and curricular autonomy for schools, enabling them to tailor participatory approaches to local community needs, while ensuring cross-sectoral coordination aligns long-term funding, professional development, and accountability frameworks to support coherent and sustained systemic innovation. This can become operative as follows:

- *Encourage pilot examples of school budgetary and curricular flexibility to adapt participatory learning approaches to local community priorities and contexts, supported by performance-based monitoring indicators.*
- *Promote interdepartmental and/or cross-sectoral working groups that bring together representatives from education, youth, and cultural sectors to develop joint action plans that outline roles, responsibilities, timelines, and resource allocations for participatory innovation practices.*

5.3 On community outreach and connections with the outside

In formal education settings the main issues were the reliance on individual initiative and short-term projects for school-community partnerships, alongside financial instability and unrecognised coordination work that undermine long-term sustainability.

Policy measures should address these issues by allocating district-level framework budgets to secure school-community partnerships and creating permanent, compensated community-liaison roles within schools to ensure sustained coordination and long-term partnership stability. This can become operative as follows:

- *Promote a recurring, protected budget line for school-community partnerships within each district's annual operational budget and allow access to it by simple, transparent procedures.*
- *Establish a standardised yet adaptable job description for a School-Community Partnership Coordinator with permanent, salaried status, and/or upskill existing staff through certified training in relational coordination, conflict mediation, participatory*

project design, and cross-sector communication, while removing teaching responsibilities and improving income benefits.

Within the non-formal educational settings, the main issues are reliance on short-term project funding that limits stability, and youth engagement models dependent on personal motivation, hindering scalability and broader systemic replication.

Policy measures could include transitioning community nonformal education grants from project-based to multiyear operational funding, and systematically disseminating successful toolkits, training pilots, and staffing models districtwide to strengthen community outreach and impact. Operational actions build on previous recommendations, and could be further strengthened as follows:

- *Audit current grant structures to identify fragmentation, gaps, and administrative burdens.*
- *Survey community organisations on the extent to which short-term funding cycles affect staff continuity, partnership depth, and programme quality.*
- *Evaluate the effects on staff retention, partnership continuity, programme innovation, and youth outcomes.*
- *Disseminate successful scaling experiences as “model briefs” with implementation checklists and decision trees to support local adaptation.*

5.4 Evaluating Democratic Critical Competences

Within formal educational contexts the main identified issues regarding democratic competences were their undervaluation and teaching difficulty, the need for applied project-based assessment, barriers to qualitative evaluation posed by curricular and capacity constraints, and the challenge of monitoring relational, implicit skills that require broader cultural shifts.

Policy measures addressing these issues could include prioritising funded teacher training to integrate democratic competences through project-based citizenship education, embedding these skills in sustained learning projects, replacing standardised tests with portfolio-based assessments, and establishing school-wide protocols for reflective dialogue that make democratic learning visible and valued. Operational actions build on previous recommendations and could be further detailed as follows:

D3.4

Policy Recommendations on the Socioeconomic Evaluation of the CCLab Model

- *Map democratic competences to curricula by identifying existing gaps, cross-referencing frameworks, and producing a competence-alignment matrix.*
- *Create a sustained, accredited training programme on facilitating project-based citizenship education, democratic pedagogies and participatory art-based methods.*
- *Develop model project pilots across subject areas that integrate democratic competences.*
- *Co-design these projects with students by involving them in issue selection, research design, presentation formats, and documented decision-making.*
- *Phase out selected standardised assessments by piloting portfolio evaluation in targeted grades or subjects and training teachers in formative assessment and moderation.*
- *Ensure consistency and transparency by establishing regional moderation panels and clearly communicating assessment changes to families and higher-education institutions.*

5.5 Sustaining Relational Infrastructures in PAR

One key insight of this SEE was to acknowledge the role of invisible relational infrastructures—trust, co-vulnerability and cultural attunement—alongside material resources, recognising that sustainable PAR is deeply political as it challenges hierarchies, standardisation and demands for scalable models.

Policy measures that address these issues should recognise trust-building and cultural responsiveness as core educational work, establish ethical and relational practice protocols for PAR, and support governance structures that share real decision-making power with students, families, and communities. Operational actions could include the following:

- *Develop professional competency frameworks that explicitly identify trust-building, emotional attunement, cultural mediation, and community-centred facilitation as essential educational skills.*
- *Review and reform university-based teacher-education curricula to include mandatory modules on relational ethics and cultural responsiveness.*

D3.4

Policy Recommendations on the Socioeconomic Evaluation of the CCLab Model

- *Fund in-service training programmes delivered by community-based organisations and experienced practitioners to strengthen community engagement and intercultural competences.*
- *Establish decision-making bodies, such as school–community councils or PAR steering committees, with formal authority over aspects of school planning, budgeting, and project prioritisation.*
- *Foster pilot-examples of school development plans that include co-created goals and strategies developed through structured participatory processes with school–community governance bodies and index of evaluation.*
- *Invest in intermediary organisations with expertise in participatory democracy, community organising, and cultural mediation to support schools in building participatory governance capacity.*

5.6 Attending to the Emotional Costs of Participation and Co-creation

Another insight of the present analysis was the recognition that the emotional labour of PAR is a systemic requirement involving vulnerability and boundary-work. Without collective support, these relational demands can lead to practitioner isolation and burnout, as institutions often shift care burdens onto educators.

Policy measures could provide structured professional development in emotional facilitation, integrate burnout-prevention and emotional-impact metrics into policy frameworks, and institutionalise team-based facilitation and peer-support structures to distribute emotional responsibility and ensure ethically sustainable PAR practice. Operative actions build on previous recommendations and include:

- *Convene a cross-sector working group to define core emotional-management competencies and create an operational framework for effective PAR facilitation.*
- *Develop simple, confidential screening tools to identify strain signals as emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation, turnover intention, among others.*
- *Ensure school evaluation and planning processes incorporate facilitator well-being, distributed emotional labour, documented sustainability strategies, and published exemplars of successful practices.*

6. Closing Remarks

To summarise this report, it is worth noting that democratic education is a structural issue that involves not only governments but society as a whole. Moreover, it has the potential to become a shared societal commitment that clarifies educational priorities, strengthens common values, and redefines expectations for both students and teachers, as posed by Mangetz et al. (2023). Schools could evolve into spaces where intellectual plurality, ethical reflection, and collaborative inquiry are central to learning. In such environments, participation would be lived rather than simulated, enabling young people to develop agency through co-creation, dialogue, and community engagement. By embracing uncertainty as an opportunity for collective imagination, education systems could nurture solidarity, critical understanding, and responsibility. This horizon reflects the transformative aspiration to which Critical ChangeLab ultimately seeks to contribute.

7. References

- Baketa, N., Jokić, B., Ristić Dedić, Z., Matić Bojić, J., Odak, I., & Šimon, J. (2024). *Policy Brief 1*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060521>
- Council of Europe. (2014). *Perspectives on Youth. Connections and Disconnections*. Volume 2. Council of Europe Publishing. <https://pjp-eu.coe.int/en/web/youth-partnership/issue-2>
- Durall Gazulla, E., Cornér, T., Niaz, Y., White, C., & Payne, E. (2024). *Critical ChangeLab Model: Framework and Toolkit*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259812>
- Durall, E., Niaz, Y., Malinverni, L., Del Razo Martínez, G. P., Porquer Rigo, J. M., Hernández Hernández, F., Raquel F. Couto, Laflin, A., Ng, J., Vasseur, E., White, C., Payne, E., & Hurley, M. (2026). *Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy: Developing 21st Century Skills for Democratic Participation*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18678282>
- Flick, U. (2015). *El diseño en Investigación Cualitativa*. Morata.
- García-Carmona, M., Marín, M. D., & Aguayo, R. (2019). Burnout syndrome in secondary school teachers: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Social Psychology of Education*, 22, 189–208. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11218-018-9471-9>
- Hernández, M. M., Pérez, J. T., Shchotkina, V., & García, D. S. (2025). Burnout syndrome in secondary school teachers: The influence of psychological capital and school type. *Edelweiss Applied Science and Technology*, 9(11), 571–580. <https://doi.org/10.55214/2576-8484.v9i11.10919>
- Jokić, B., Matić Bojić, J., Ristić Dedić, Z., & Baketa, N. (2024a). *Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ) and Democracy Health Index (DHI)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060480>
- Jokić, B., Ristić Dedić, Z., Matić Bojić, J., Baketa, N., Odak, I., & Šimon, J. (2024b). *Youth Perspectives on Everyday Democracy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060503>
- Jokić, B., Ristić Dedić, Z., Matić Bojić, J., Odak, I., Šimon, J., & Lovrečki, K. (2024c). *Everyday democracy in formal and non-formal education institutions*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060500>

D3.4

Policy Recommendations on the Socioeconomic Evaluation of the CCLab Model

Mangez, E., Draelants, H., Dumay, X., & Verhoeven, M. (Eds.). (2023). *L'école face à la complexité: Désinstitutionnalisation, globalisation, accélération*. De Boeck Supérieur.

Milanese, N., & Critical ChangeLab. (2025). *Policy Recommendations on Citizenship Education for Sustainable European Democracy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17312757>

Palka, J. (2024) The Potential of Participatory Social Economics: a Framework and Feminist Perspective. *Forum for Social Economics*, 53(2), 141–169, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07360932.2024.2329875>

Sancho-Gil, J. M., & Rivera-Vargas, P. J. (2016). The socio-economic evaluation of a European project: The DIYLab case. *Informatics*, 3(3), 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics3030013>

Woodgate, R. L., Tennent, P., & Barriage, S. (2020). Creating Space for Youth Voice: Implications of Youth Disclosure Experiences for Youth-Centered Research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406920958974>

Annexes

Annex I. Script for Interview

General information	
Status/Position of Interviewed Person	
Institution	
Date	
Place	

Addressing Issue I	
Theme	Questions
Diagnosis of similar projects in local environments	Are you aware of any initiatives currently in place in your context focused on youth democratic participation, art-based methods and active citizenship?
	If so, how have those programs fit within your school/department schedules and priorities?

Addressing Issue II	
Theme	Questions
Economic and structural constraints of standardized systems regarding time and curricula	Do you think your institution/department has the capacity and willingness to implement a program like the CCLab? Yes/No, Why?
	What institutional barriers might hinder its implementation?
	What benefits would you expect for students and for the institution, teachers, the wider school community and for society in general?

Addressing Issue III
Contextualization to address the issue: As an outcome of the CCLab project, evidence showed that artistic and participatory research-based methods are highly effective in fostering student engagement in democratic practices. However, it also became clear that many teachers felt they lacked the necessary tools, skills, and confidence to apply these methods in their classrooms. This highlights the need for targeted teacher training on these aspects.

Addressing Issue III	
Theme	Questions
Continuous Teacher/Facilitator training in democratic awareness, active citizenship and creative practices	How relevant do you perceive training teachers on these aspects (art-based methods and participatory research-based methods) to be for your school/educational context?
	In your opinion, which aspects of these approaches would be most relevant or priority?
	What barriers or challenges do you see in implementing or expanding such initiatives?
	What are the costs (not only economic but also in terms of infrastructure and human resources) associated with teacher development in these aspects?
	Do you think it would be feasible for your institution or department to assume these costs?

Addressing Issue IV	
Contextualization to address the issue: The CCLab consists of a series of phases or steps, one of which is "Act", in which young participants transform their ideas into tangible actions. This phase did not always run smoothly due to lack of connections outside of the institution where the CCLabs took place.	
Theme	Questions
Connections with the outside	Are you aware of any initiatives in your context where schools have established long-term partnerships with local communities?
	If so, what barriers or challenges have you observed when trying to develop these partnerships?
	What benefits have you observed from developing these partnerships?
	What are the resources or costs that would be required to establish and maintain these long-term partnerships with local NGOs, businesses, community centers in order to connect school learning with real-world situations?

Addressing Issue V	
Theme	Questions
	Do the following competences promoted by CCLab resonate with your understanding of what students should develop? Critical Understanding

Addressing Issue V	
Theme	Questions
Evaluation of critical competences	of the world, Imagination and creativity capacity, Transformative agency and Democratic disposition.
	From your perspective, does it make sense to evaluate these competences in schools?
	What are the costs of qualitative and continuous evaluation on the aforementioned competences?

